

**The Politicisation of Research
Funding in Britain: An Analysis of
UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)
Grants and Policies**

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Courage
Freedom
Truth

Executive Summary

- UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), which manages £8.8 billion in government funds, has become politicised, diverting significant amounts of money and attention to culturally left-wing Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) initiatives.
- Social justice terms (such as equity, diversity and inclusion) have surged in UKRI grants, up 35 times since 2000, and nearly doubling between 2020 and 2024. This reveals how scholar activist interests and UKRI funding signals have ideologically distorted the research enterprise.
- Mentions of ‘equality’ are more common in UKRI web pages between 2020 and 2025 than mentions of ‘excellence’, and the balance has been growing increasingly skewed.
- Politicisation of research is set to dramatically increase with Research Excellence Framework (REF) 2029, which allocates £2 billion in competitive funding to universities. REF 2029 will be considerably more EDI-focused than previous rounds. The research ‘Environment’ criterion has been changed to ‘*People, Culture and Environment*’ (PCE) and carries a larger weight of 25 percent, up from 15 percent in 2021. EDI will be central to achieving a higher score, with ‘EDI data’ explicitly listed as one of the factors that is likely to be assessed.
- A keyword search of UKRI’s EDI policy report shows that gender is mentioned 200 times, race or ethnicity 73 times and class just 3 times (the latter largely to emphasise that virtually no EDI initiatives have focused on class).
- UKRI documents reveal close links with overtly culturally left-wing EDI kitemarking organisations such as Athena SWAN (for gender) and the Race Equality Charter. These have directly collaborated with UKRI in the crafting of UKRI’s EDI policies.
- The politicisation of the research funding process threatens to undermine the fragile cross-party consensus that has existed to date in the UK in favour of science and research funding – as has already occurred in the US. It threatens public trust in universities.
- This report recommends that government cease funding EDI initiatives within UKRI and its component councils unless EDI can be shown in randomised control trials to measurably improve research excellence.

- The report recommends that UKRI rewrite its REF 2029 guidance to eliminate EDI from the research scoring process and refocus the evaluation criteria for research environment on excellence, as well as restoring the 60 percent weighting given to submitted outputs that prevailed in REF2021.
- The report recommends the removal of race and gender targets across UKRI and its component councils unless justified by experimental or multivariate large-N models showing significant evidence of discrimination that cannot be addressed by unobtrusive measures.
- The report recommends an independent and politically balanced parliamentary commission comprised of non-academics without ties to the sector to conduct a full audit of EDI spending and to investigate whether funding priorities have skewed too far toward the cultural left.
- The report recommends new funding initiatives for neglected non-leftist priorities such as national attachment, cohesion and competitiveness; traditional approaches to arts and humanities; the study of left-wing populism and extremism; or the nature of virtue and beauty.
- The report calls for quantitative publication metrics to play a major role in REF 2029 to advance fairness and merit while reducing cost.
- The report recommends that disparities not be used as evidence of discrimination until experimental or large-N multivariate analyses demonstrate this to be the case.
- The report calls for a rebalancing of EDI away from gender and race toward political diversity, parental occupation, class and other less characteristics that are less salient for the cultural left.

Introduction

This study examines the politicisation of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) within the 2000–2025 time period using big data analysis and qualitative investigation of UKRI web pages.

Contested Values

At the heart of the report is an acknowledgement that there is a philosophical clash between the positive-sum cultural flourishing perspective favoured by a majority of the public, and the zero-sum cultural socialist perspective endorsed by an important tranche of academics – especially those who self-select onto committees within academic bodies, unions and professional organizations. For instance, around 3 in 4 social science and humanities academics in British universities identify as on the political left, and a slight preponderance of left academics in Anglosphere universities endorse cultural socialist policies such as affirmative action and mandatory diversity statements.¹

As with the equity-efficiency tradeoff in economics, there is an extent to which redistribution is welfare-enhancing, but beyond an optimum point, egalitarianism reduces human flourishing. If a system is permitted to tilt in the direction of socialism, it crowds out wealth, impeding utility maximisation.² As in economics, so too in culture. Restrictions on speech and resources in the name of redistribution and harm protection for historically marginalised race, gender and sexual identity groups smother academic freedom and divert resources that would otherwise fuel innovation and human progress.³

The debate between EDI, favoured by many in the academic policy establishment, and the Merit, Equality and Individuality (MEI) position endorsed by most of the public, is political. As Table 1 illustrates, cultural socialists prefer EDI over MEI, and equality of outcome over trait-blind equal treatment. Their research priorities include equal representation by race and sex among those receiving research funding; a concentration on ‘systemic’ (typically unmeasurable) axes of oppression over measurable individual-level discrimination; and concentrating more funding on inequality and harm protection for minority identity groups than on expanding excellence, wealth, innovation, beauty, cohesion, freedom and truth.

¹ Kaufmann, E., ‘The Politics of the Culture Wars in Contemporary Britain,’ *Policy Exchange*, November 19, 2022. <https://policyexchange.org.uk/publication/the-politics-of-the-culture-wars-in-contemporary-britain/>; Kaufmann, E. (2021). "Academic freedom in crisis: Punishment, political discrimination, and self-censorship." *Center for the Study of Partisanship and Ideology* 2: 1-195. <https://www.cspicenter.com/p/academic-freedom-in-crisis-punishment>

² Le Grand, J. (1990). "Equity versus efficiency: the elusive trade-off." *Ethics* 100(3): 554-568.

³ Kaufmann, E. P. (2024). *Taboo: How making race sacred produced a cultural revolution*, Forum.

EDI proponents rarely acknowledge the equity-efficiency tradeoff, averring that equity improves excellence. However, beneath the rhetoric, advocates almost never provide robust quantitative analysis to back up their claims.⁴ Evidence that men are cited more than women might be viewed as resulting from personal choices that correlate with sex, or it could be the result of sexist citation bias – the position favoured by those in the ‘citation justice’ movement.⁵ If the latter argument is false, however, and there is no rigorous evidence that it is true, then any moves toward enforced equal representation by sex will result in lower academic output.⁶ In effect, there will be an equity-efficiency tradeoff in a situation where the public prefer to fund research productivity over research equity.

A good example of the rising academic emphasis on equal outcomes comes from American sociologist Musa al-Gharbi, who finds that the proportion of articles in the top four sociology journals that mention ‘equality’ has risen steadily over past decades to reach a staggering 85 percent. Almost all sociology research is now explicitly focused on left-wing priorities.⁷ While this proportion may not be as high outside the social sciences and humanities, it is indicative of what happens when cultural left priorities dominate scholarship.

In this report, I examine a series of indicators that demonstrate a sharp rise in cultural socialist research in UKRI funding, revealing a set of priorities that do not match those of the British public. Should taxpayers be funding politicized research at a time of cultural contestation and economic hardship? What are the implications of this for public trust in academia and support for R &D, much of which is vital for the British economy and advancement of humanity?

⁴ Singal, Jesse, ‘What if Diversity Training Is Doing More Harm Than Good?’, *New York Times*, 17 January 2023. <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/01/17/opinion/dei-trainings-effective.html>; Al-Gharbi, Musa, ‘Diversity is Important. Diversity-Related Training is Terrible.’ *Musaalgharbi.com*, 16 September 2020. <https://www.mindingthecampus.org/2020/11/06/diversity-is-important-diversity-related-training-is-terrible/>

⁵ Lopez-Lloreda, Claudia, ‘Women researchers are cited less than men. Here’s why—and what can be done about it,’ *Science*, October 13, 2022 <https://www.science.org/content/article/women-researchers-cited-less-men-heres-why-what-can-done>; ‘Citation Justice – what it is and how you can practice it,’ University of Birmingham, 1 November, 2023. <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/news/2023/citation-justice-what-it-is-and-how-you-can-practice-it>

⁶ Abbot, D., et al. (2023). "In defense of merit in science." *Journal of Controversial Ideas* 3(1). <https://journalofcontroversialideas.org/article/3/1/236>

⁷ ‘A Discipline in Disarray? The State of Sociology,’ *American Enterprise Institute*, April 30, 2025 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HCjG-191Zhc>

Table 1. Competing Values in Research

	<i>Cultural Socialist</i>	<i>Cultural Flourishing</i>
Cardinal Value	Equity	Excellence
Research Agenda	Reducing inequality	Expanding human possibility
Conception of Social Justice	Equality of outcome	Equality of opportunity
Orientations to speech and truth	Emotional harm protection for marginalized groups, speech codes, subjective truth	Expectations of reasonable resilience, freedom of speech, objective truth
Policy Aim	Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI)	Merit, Equality and Individuality (MEI)

UKRI

UKRI is Britain’s national funding agency for investing in science and research. It encompasses 7 Research Councils, including the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC), Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC), Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC), Medical Research Council (MRC), Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) and Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC). In addition, UKRI includes Innovate UK and Research England. Operating across the entirety of the UK, it has a combined annual budget of £8.8 billion.

Background: the Rise of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI)

In recent years, UKRI has begun to devote increasing attention to EDI. Momentum has arguably been driven by activist administrators and academics within the academic system, a majority of whom support EDI. For instance, by a 2-to-1 margin, social science and humanities academics at top universities in the UK, US, Canada and Australia endorse the use of mandatory diversity statements, which force job and grant applicants to pledge to uphold the culturally left idea of equal results for identity groups. By a 44-30 margin, British social science and humanities academics also support the use of race and gender quotas for class reading lists. Most endorse the use of social pressure or institutional punishment to enforce

compliance.⁸

As both measures are politically coded and polarising, and represent ‘equal results’ rather than ‘equal opportunities’ logic, they amount to a clear violation of the University of Chicago Kalven Report (1967) principle that institutions should not take positions on contested political issues.⁹ They infringe the freedom of conscience of individuals, discriminate on the basis of philosophical belief and thereby abrogate academic freedom.

EDI initiatives are political, not consensus, values, because they a) move beyond equal opportunity to a focus on obtaining equal results, which is deemed more important than equal treatment and often violates it; b) view protecting sensitive members of designated minority groups from offense, i.e. ‘emotional safety’, or anticipating the often unmeasured and complex downstream effects of research, as more important than freedom of expression and the pursuit of truth. Both aims further what Jonathan Haidt terms the equality and care/harm moral foundations, which underpin the values of the contemporary left, especially the identity-focused cultural left.¹⁰

The rise of EDI reaches back to the 1960s in the United States, with the advent of affirmative action and racial sensitivity training. Human resources and legal compliance professionals led the way, with the Supreme Court taking its lead from ‘best practices’ in the emerging sensitivity training and human resources sector. Court decisions on ‘disparate impact’ and ‘hostile environment’ were used by professionals to push policies beyond the remit of court decisions. Their innovations later came to influence the courts, such that firms which could show that they had adopted sensitivity (rebadged in the 1990s as ‘diversity’) training and ‘goals and timetables’ for equal group outcomes could reduce their liability in discrimination cases and class-action lawsuits.¹¹ Even when the Supreme Court rolled back the scope of EDI, as under the Reagan presidency, large firms and other organisations continued to expand their use of these practices, showing that culture and ideology, more than legal compliance, was the main engine of change.¹²

In Britain, the 1975 UK Sex Discrimination Act and 1976 Race Relations Act, followed by European Union jurisprudence, advanced the concept of ‘indirect discrimination’, that is, restrictions on using qualifications which have a disparate impact

⁸ Kaufmann, E. (2021). "Academic Freedom in crisis: punishment, political discrimination, and self-censorship." *Center for the Study of Partisanship and Ideology* 2: 44-45; Goodwin, M. (2022). "Is Academic Freedom Under Threat?," Legatum Institute, January.

<https://www.prosperity.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Legatum-Institute-Is-Academic-Freedom-Under-Threat.pdf>

⁹ ‘Report on the University's Role in Political and Social Action,’ University of Chicago, February 1967.

<https://provost.uchicago.edu/reports/report-universitys-role-political-and-social-action>

¹⁰ Haidt, J. (2012). *The righteous mind : why good people are divided by politics and religion*. London, Allen Lane.

¹¹ Dobbin, F. (2009). *Inventing equal opportunity*. *Inventing Equal Opportunity*, Princeton University Press.

¹² Lehman, Charles F. (2021). ‘The Genealogy of Woke Capital,’ *City-Journal*, Autumn 2021. <https://www.city-journal.org/article/the-genealogy-of-woke-capital>

on particular groups. However, disparate impacts are not illegal, as the law requires the plaintiff to justify why disparate impacts are discriminatory. Even so, activist lawyers and campaigners tend to move beyond the law to argue that disparate outcomes by group represent an ipso facto violation of ‘substantive equality.’ The Equality Act (2010) supercharged this logic through the Public Sector Equality Duty (PSED), which applies to universities and contributed to a similar judicial-administrative ratcheting process as transpired in America. While the act enacts a positive duty on employers to advance the cause of protected groups, the parameters for doing so are not specified or ring-fenced, opening space for activists to press maximal claims.

In British academia, the same logic is evident, whereby organisations move ahead of the law while claiming to be merely complying with it. Thus the UKRI’s 2019 *Equality, diversity and inclusion in research and innovation: UK review* references the 2010 Equality Act 11 times to justify its culturally left-wing innovations which do not stem from any explicit provision in the Act. Monitoring of awards by race, sex and disability, for instance, is justified by UKRI by referring to the Equality Act.¹³

Advance HE and UKRI

Significantly, the UKRI’s position paper on EDI was published in collaboration with Advance HE, a multi-million pound organisation funded by contributions from universities which describes itself as a ‘single sector agency for equality and diversity, learning and teaching, and leadership and governance in higher education.’¹⁴ Advance HE is the cockpit of the EDI industry in British higher education.

Advance HE’s Race Equality Charter (REC) alleges systemic racism within the academic sector, yet, as Professor Doug Stokes of the University of Exeter notes, data shows that minorities are actually overrepresented among academics. Advance HE acknowledges that the share of minority academics (at all levels) increased from 8 to 14 percent between 2003 and 2017, yet because the share of BAME (Black and Minority Ethnic) academics who are professors is slightly below that of whites (9.7 vs 11.1), this is used to claim that ‘racial inequalities are a significant issue within higher education.’ The single-minded focus on decontextualised bivariate statistics that support a narrative of systemic racism (while ignoring countervailing evidence), with no attempt to take socioeconomic or interest and choice-led dynamics into account; or to

¹³ ‘Diversity Data,’ *UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)*, accessed 3 November 2025. <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/supporting-healthy-research-and-innovation-culture/equality-diversity-and-inclusion/diversity-data/why-we-collect-diversity-data/#contents-list>

¹⁴ ‘Race Equality Charter | Advance HE’. Accessed 29 August 2022. <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/equality-charters/race-equality-charter>.

consider ethnic shifts among younger staff that are likely to produce change at senior levels only over time; speaks to confirmation bias as its overriding heuristic rather than adherence to principles of the scientific method such as falsifiability or addressing competing explanations.¹⁵

Stokes outlines an EDI industry in academia coordinated by Advance HE, whose kitemarking schemes, notably Athena SWAN for gender and the REC for race, interface with increasingly influential EDI committees within each university and research council. These local committees create an institutional imperative to achieve the top ‘gold’ ranking from the Athena SWAN or REC schemes. These awards in turn form part of university department’s research and teaching assessment narratives which affect their ranking in league tables. Departments’ research narratives are also used as part of research assessment (REF) to formally rank institutions so as to allocate £2 billion in UKRI QR block grant research funding to universities.

Best practice in scoring highly on the Athena SWAN and Race Equality Charter schemes involves cultural socialist initiatives such as ‘decolonising the curriculum’, mainstreaming critical race and gender perspectives, and improving race/gender-specific representation - all of which incentivize hiring and promotion policies that may violate individuals’ right to equal treatment. Institutions are implored to address ‘microaggressions’ as well as their racial awarding gap. This is purportedly caused by systemic discrimination, a concept which lacks validity and robust empirical evidence. While there are no concrete pedagogical yardsticks listed under the scoring schemes (thereby allowing Advance HE to publicly deny *de jure* support for critical race theory and other radical ideas while *de facto* supporting it), the ranking of institutions systematically favours those that implement radical left-wing ideas – and these ideas are promoted by AdvanceHE through its provision of information to disseminate ‘best practice’.¹⁶ Note the strong emphasis on both the equality of outcome (race/gender equity) and care/harm (microaggressions, hostile environment) moral foundations.

Advance HE offers resources to prod EDI committees in universities to advance the agenda of the cultural left. Namely centering equal outcomes and emotional harm protection for race, gender and sexual groups above other social or psychological categories such as class or having academic parents. A ‘majority-minority’ binary¹⁷ frame is used rather than

¹⁵ Stokes, Doug, ‘The campus grievance industry,’ *The Critic*, November 2020. <https://thecritic.co.uk/issues/september-2020/the-campus-grievance-industry/>

¹⁶ Stokes, Doug, *Against Decolonisation: Campus Culture Wars and the Decolonisation of the West*, Polity Press, 2023; Advance HE Report, ‘Kingston University’s project: Decolonising the science curriculum,’ 18 February 2022. <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/knowledge-hub/kingston-universitys-project-decolonising-science-curriculum>; Gann, N., ‘Cultural competency, racial trauma and decolonising the curriculum,’ *Advance HE*, 17 December, 2020. <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/news-and-views/Cultural-competency-racial-trauma-and-decolonising-the-curriculum>

¹⁷ Sakamoto, A., et al. (2022). "The socioeconomic attainments of second-generation Southeast Asian Americans in the 21st century: Evidence from the American Community Survey, 2012–2016." *Population Research and Policy Review* 41(1): 59-88.

a more accurate portrayal in which all groups exhibit a degree of bias against all groups.

Another cultural leftist aim is ‘decolonisation’: prioritising group representation, anti-majoritarianism and equal outcomes above scholastic merit on reading lists. This combines with a negative moralising approach to the western past rather than a fully-contextualised one that locates positive and negative episodes - such as slavery and colonisation - among all civilisations. One REC survey of ‘REC contacts’ in partner universities who were intending to join the scheme asked individuals about their institutions’ motivation, asking if they agreed with a range of motives. 94 percent agreed that a reason for joining was because ‘our institution wants to decolonise the curriculum, teaching and learning.’ A further 78 percent said it was important that their institution respond positively to the (overtly political, and scandal-plagued) Black Lives Matter movement.¹⁸ Many had already taken steps to prepare for coveted REC membership, with nearly 2 in 3 saying they were already implementing decolonisation and nearly half saying they had engaged the services of diversity and equity consultants.¹⁹ The frequency of a range of actions undertaken by universities seeking REC membership is illustrated in Figure 1. This illustrates the kind of behaviour and expenditure that the REC is incentivizing across the sector.

Figure 1

Source: Oloyede, Freya Douglas, Ashlee Christoffersen and Tinu Cornish, *Race Equality Charter Review*, Advance HE,

¹⁸ Lynch, J. and A. Fahlberg, ‘[Justice Department Investigates Black Lives Matter Leaders for Potential Fraud](#),’ *National Review*, October 30, 2025

¹⁹ Oloyede, Freya Douglas, Ashlee Christoffersen and Tinu Cornish, *Race Equality Charter Review*, Advance HE, March 2021, p. 19. <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/knowledge-hub/race-equality-charter-review-phase-2>

Advance HE initiatives feed back into higher education institutions to assist in making the case for more radical forms of EDI. The net result is a self-propelling ratchet which tends toward the institutional prioritisation of EDI at the expense of equal treatment, academic freedom and excellence.

As part of his ‘war on waste’ in the NHS, Sajid Javid abolished several EDI positions in the health service. However, every branch of every public body, council and university has a EDI payroll. Thus not only UKRI, but its component research councils, maintain their own EDI infrastructure. As a result, Karl Williams estimates that the public sector EDI payroll runs to between £200 million and £2 billion per annum.²⁰

This is an enormous sum to commit during a time of austerity, especially when the evidence shows that EDI achieves none of its stated aims (i.e. improving inter-group relations, aiding minority group performance) and can lead to more self-conscious and tense inter-group interactions.²¹ For instance, British workers who have taken diversity training are more fearful of being fired or facing a detriment for speech; and much more reluctant to criticize a black co-worker, arguably impeding the necessary workplace feedback to help minorities narrow performance and evaluation gaps.²²

The links between public university-funded EDI bodies (Advance HE) and Britain’s research funding councils (UKRI) are very close. UKRI’s recent general review urges: ‘Funders should ensure that application processes support their commitments to equality, diversity and inclusion.’²³ In its 2021 document *Preventing harm (safeguarding) in research and innovation policy*, UKRI leans into the radical doctrine of emotional safety that opens the door to subjective and expansive definitions of harm which threaten academic freedom and the presumption of innocence: ‘“Harm” is any detrimental effect on psychological, physical or emotional wellbeing...Harm may be caused by abuse or exploitation, whether intended or unintended.’ UKRI favours a ‘survivor-centred approach’ which ‘means putting the rights, needs and wishes of the victim or survivor of the exploitation, abuse or harm at the centre of an organisation’s thinking’ (p. 19). This culturally left-wing

²⁰ Williams, Karl, ‘The fractal blob: how EDI has crept into every level of the public sector,’ Capx, 13 June, 2022. <https://capx.co/the-fractal-blob-how-edi-has-crept-into-every-level-of-the-public-sector>

²¹ Singal, Jesse, ‘What if Diversity Training Is Doing More Harm Than Good?’, *New York Times*, 17 January 2023. <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/01/17/opinion/dei-trainings-effective.html>; Al-Gharbi, Musa, ‘Diversity is Important. Diversity-Related Training is Terrible.’ *Musaalgharbi.com*, 16 September 2020. <https://www.mindingthecampus.org/2020/11/06/diversity-is-important-diversity-related-training-is-terrible/>

²² Kaufmann, E., ‘The Politics of the Culture Wars in Contemporary Britain,’ *Policy Exchange*, November 19, 2022. <https://policyexchange.org.uk/publication/the-politics-of-the-culture-wars-in-contemporary-britain/>

²³ ‘Independent Review of Research Bureaucracy: Final Report,’ UKRI, November 2022, p. 8. <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/62e234da8fa8f5033275fc32/independent-review-research-bureaucracy-final-report.pdf>

doctrine of emotional safety sits in direct contravention of universities' duty to promote free speech and academic freedom, enshrined in the Higher Education (Freedom of Speech) Act of 2023.

The 2019 UKRI report, *Equality, diversity and inclusion in research and innovation: UK review* is written by Advance HE for UKRI. Little wonder that it references Advance HE 55 times and Athena SWAN 32 times.²⁴ As Figure 2 shows, a keyword search of the report shows that it centres gender and race over disability and other characteristics, with just 3 mentions of socioeconomic status. The latter did not concern actual actions but only the observation that class had not hitherto been considered in any EDI activity.

Figure 2

Source: Calculated from *Equality, diversity and inclusion in research and innovation: UK review* (UKRI/Advance HE 2019).

The report also analysed a large number of organisational interventions in the EDI space. They found that over 40 percent of the interventions focused on gender, 9 percent on race, ethnicity or nationality and 1 percent on age, with no attention to class.²⁵

²⁴ Guyan, Kevin and Freya Douglas Oloyede, 'Equality, diversity and inclusion in research and innovation: UK review,' Advance HE/UKRI 2019. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/UKRI-020920-EDI-EvidenceReviewUK.pdf](https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/UKRI-020920-EDI-EvidenceReviewUK.pdf)

²⁵ Ibid., p. 15.

This focus is political and ideological. How so? The centering of gender and race, prioritizing it far ahead of class, involves prioritisation, and thus a ranking of competing values. One could equally imagine focusing on the overrepresentation of those with academic parents (present at a rate as much as 25 times above the average), or the underrepresentation of groups such as religious people, conservatives (who comprise barely 10 percent of academics), Gypsy and Irish Travelers, those from the Celtic periphery or rural people.²⁶ The salience of race and gender in contemporary cultural progressive ideology, a legacy of the post-1960s turn of the left, explains their dominance in the UKRI's organisational imperatives.²⁷ Surveys show large splits by vote and ideology over these policy preferences: they are irreducibly political.²⁸

UKRI is swiftly moving beyond words to action. £8 million was spent on 13 projects during 2021-25 focusing on 'Widening participation in postgraduate research.'²⁹ A joint UKRI-British Academy 'EDI Caucus' scheme in 2022 offered £4.6 million for university-based bidders 'to lead on providing high quality research evidence on equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) that informs policy and practice in the research and innovation system.'³⁰ The latter could have concentrated squarely on empirical evidence of what works. However, the evaluation process was heavily steered by cultural socialist ideology and the incorporation of intellectually unrigorous 'critical' qualitative perspectives that have been the source of many problems with the implementation of EDI.³¹

To take a specific example of how funds are being spent to advance cultural left perspectives in the British institutional research enterprise we can examine how one UKRI research council, the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), seeks to increase the ethnic diversity of students supported through its doctoral fellowship programme. Its plan requires all universities submitting applications for ESRC doctoral studentships to provide EDI action plans, 'to be reviewed annually, as an assessed part of their bid for funding. This should include information on how they will encourage applications from under-represented groups.'

ESRC instituted a set of workshops for universities to 'explore how [they] can make entry requirements more inclusive,

²⁶ Morgan, A. C., et al. (2022). "Socioeconomic roots of academic faculty." *Nature Human Behaviour*: 1-9.

²⁷ Hobsbawm, E. (1996). "Identity politics and the left." *New Left Review*: 38-47.

²⁸ Kaufmann, E., 'The Politics of the Culture Wars in Contemporary Britain,' *Policy Exchange*, November 19, 2022. <https://policyexchange.org.uk/publication/the-politics-of-the-culture-wars-in-contemporary-britain/>; Kaufmann, E. (2021). "Academic freedom in crisis: Punishment, political discrimination, and self-censorship." *Center for the Study of Partisanship and Ideology* 2: 1-195. <https://www.cspicenter.com/p/academic-freedom-in-crisis-punishment>

²⁹ 'UKRI equality diversity and inclusion strategy: draft for consultation,' 13 January 2022. <https://www.ukri.org/publications/equality-diversity-and-inclusion-strategy-draft-for-consultation/ukri-equality-diversity-and-inclusion-strategy-draft-for-consultation/>

³⁰ 'Equality, diversity and inclusion caucus,' UKRI, accessed 11 May 2023. <https://www.ukri.org/opportunity/equality-diversity-and-inclusion-caucus/>

³¹ Singal, Jesse, 'What if Diversity Training Is Doing More Harm Than Good?,' *New York Times*, 17 January, 2023. <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/01/17/opinion/dei-trainings-effective.html>

with greater focus on assessing potential.’ In 2022, the panel reviewing the REF claimed that ‘excellence’ based on publication metrics represented a form of ‘epistemic injustice’ that should be replaced by ‘evaluative diversity’, with a heavy push for more EDI.³² This proposes a watering down of criteria for excellence in order to increase race and gender diversity for weaker applicants. At the same time, it introduced entry requirements that, *de facto*, politically discriminate against classical liberal, traditional socialist or conservative researchers who oppose the idea of trying to engineer equal results across politically salient New Left identity categories such as gender and race.

The ESRC declares that a key measure of success is for the ESRC to ‘[establish] minimum and stretch targets for recruitment of under-represented groups.’ Success must involve ‘measurable improvements in the diversity of our workforce over the next 3 years.’ This represents a clear ‘goals and timetables’ agenda based on a value hierarchy in which equal results trump equal opportunities. No caveat is provided to the effect that explicit racial discrimination is out of bounds. There is no recognition that such social engineering runs up against limits in equality law, as with the court ruling against the RAF for employing diversity targets which unlawfully discriminate against white men.³³ The authors similarly fail to specify that equality goals should not come at the expense of research excellence. Yet race and gender favouritism is necessarily zero-sum in a context of finite resources: the positive focus on marginalised groups represents a sleight-of-hand concealing a dark underbelly of anti-white, anti-male and sometimes anti-Asian discrimination.

The ESRC seeks to embed EDI principles in researchers’ proposals, including the requirement to ‘[engage] research users and key stakeholders from the initial planning phases onwards...Applicants should also demonstrate how they will build inclusive teams that support the career development of all members.’ Teams must ‘demonstrate an inclusive approach to research design’ and a ‘supportive research culture’.

These are loosely-defined aims which open the process up to concept creep and an EDI arms race. All of which violates dissenting researchers’ freedom of conscience and their academic freedom (what if the research offends a ‘stakeholder’?). This in order to uphold the contested cultural socialist notion of emotional safety. ESRC urges that the assessment of proposals take EDI into account, injecting principles other than excellence into their evaluation process. This skews the research that ultimately gets funded, in what is an extremely competitive process with success rates than may dip as low as

³² Curry, S., Gadd, E & Wilsdon, J. (2022). *Harnessing the Metric Tide: indicators, infrastructures & priorities for UK responsible research assessment. Report of The Metric Tide Revisited panel*, December 2022. ISBN 978-1-7397102-1-7. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21701624>.

https://rori.figshare.com/articles/report/Harnessing_the_Metric_Tide/21701624?file=38515103

³³ Beale, Jonathan, ‘RAF diversity targets discriminated against white men,’ *BBC*, 29 June 2023. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-66060490>

10 percent of applications.³⁴

Even more concerning is the aim to compel researchers to complete equality impact assessments (EIAs). The ESRC's success criteria include the goal of 'publishing EIAs for all new funding opportunities and strategies, ensuring a systematic and transparent approach to embedding EDI considerations in our decision making.'³⁵ This means that EDI 'goals and timetables' logic will be pushed for the most politically-important cultural left categories (gender, race) while less salient categories are ignored. There is no caveat that this should be subordinate to research quality and academic freedom if there is conflict between competing objectives.

The end result will be to compel researchers to skew their research teams and work in a way that is suboptimal for Britain's national interest in maximising research output – thereby affecting the value that taxpayers derive from scientific research funds. Pressure from administrators or mentors on applicants to revise their applications to meet such goals may also violate the provisions of the Higher Education Freedom of Speech Act.

Perhaps no council has been as radical as the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC), arguably due to the relatively low proportion of women in STEM fields. This body, referencing the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology's R&D People and Culture Strategy, has outlined a series of EDI 'Expectations':

Theme 1: Develop an approach to embedding EDI in the research lifecycle

Theme 2: Implement good practices in recruitment and selection processes to ensure diverse teams

Theme 3: Ensure diversity and inclusivity in all activities such as events, sandpits, networking

Theme 4: Create an inclusive and accessible environment

Theme 5: Ensure career progression and training for all members of the team

Theme 6: Inclusive research

The EPSRC have a target of at least 30 percent women on review panels, with no all-male panels – goals that have apparently been met and surpassed. Targets for their Peer Review College and Strategic Advisory Teams are for 30 percent

³⁴ 'ESRC equality, diversity and inclusion living action plan 2023 to 2025,' ESRC, 23 March 2023.

<https://www.ukri.org/publications/esrc-equality-diversity-and-inclusion-action-plan/esrc-equality-diversity-and-inclusion-living-action-plan-2023-to-2025/>

³⁵ Ibid. 'Using Equality Impact Assessments,' UKRI, accessed 1 November, 2025. <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/supporting-healthy-research-and-innovation-culture/equality-diversity-and-inclusion/esrc/esrc-equality-impact-assessments/#contents-list>

women and 20 percent ethnic minorities. For their Strategic Advisory Network and Science Engineering and Technology Board, the goals, set in 2021, are a more ambitious 40 percent women and 20 percent ethnic minorities.³⁶ It is unclear if these numbers are plucked from the air, if they correspond to some reference population, and, if so, why this is a defensible notion of what a ‘natural’ unbiased pipeline should look like.

The EPSRC is also operating with a conception of peer review bias which has no basis in empirical evidence since the recent research finds no consistent evidence of anti-female discrimination in academia.³⁷ Undeterred, EPSRC is determined to ‘understand the depth of implicit reviewer bias’ and is willing to use ‘alternate approaches’ to meritocratic peer review, as well as trialing ‘Unconscious Bias Observers’ in funding panels.³⁸ This regardless of the fact that empirical measures of implicit bias have been shown to be unreliable.³⁹ There could also be legal risk if such practices result in indirect discrimination toward white, male or heterosexual researchers. Again, despite the lack of any evidence-based substrate, these expensive and time-consuming approaches continue to be pursued by UKRI’s research councils. This is a product of ideology and internal political pressure, not scientific evidence.

Research Assessment Framework (REF) 2029

The Research Assessment Framework (REF) is a highly competitive and consequential exercise that determines the distribution of around £2 billion in research funding to universities, outside the research councils. It is hotly contested and universities spent an estimated £454 million preparing for REF 2021.⁴⁰

The REF has had a focus on EDI since the 2021 exercise. As Elizabeth Gadd remarks, ‘REF 2021 already placed a significant focus on EDI. Equality Impact Assessments had to be performed at every stage of the submission, EDI training for REF decision-makers was an essential requirement for even submitting to the REF, and both institution- and unit-level environment statements demanded narratives as to how equality and diversity in research careers were promoted across the

³⁶ EPSRC, ‘Expectations for equality, diversity and inclusion,’ accessed 8 October, 2025. <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/supporting-healthy-research-and-innovation-culture/equality-diversity-and-inclusion/epsrc/expectations-for-equality-diversity-and-inclusion/>

³⁷ Ceci, S. J., et al. (2023). "Exploring gender bias in six key domains of academic science: An adversarial collaboration." *Psychological Science in the Public Interest* 24(1): 15-73.

³⁸ EPSRC, ‘Expectations for equality, diversity and inclusion’, accessed 16 October, 2025. <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/supporting-healthy-research-and-innovation-culture/equality-diversity-and-inclusion/epsrc/expectations-for-equality-diversity-and-inclusion/>

³⁹ Jussim, L., ‘12 Reasons to Be Skeptical of Common Claims About Implicit Bias,’ *Psychology Today*, March 28, 2022. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/gb/blog/rabble-rouser/202203/12-reasons-be-skeptical-common-claims-about-implicit-bias>

⁴⁰ Grove, Jack, ‘Universities spent average of £3 million each on 2021 REF,’ *Times Higher*, 13 July, 2023. <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/news/universities-spent-average-ps3-million-each-2021-ref>

institution.’⁴¹

Even so, the EDI component is set to rise substantially. As Iain Mansfield writes:

Research England is piloting new metrics for how it will allocate funding, such as the proportion of research staff who are women or from ethnic minorities, as well as details on mean and median pay gaps. They want ‘documented evidence that leadership of EDI initiatives is appropriately recognised (e.g. in workloads or promotion criteria)’ and that staff are trained on ‘EDI principles’. They want carbon emissions data and evidence of ‘academic citizenship’. They want evidence of participation in initiatives such as the Athena Swan or Race Equality Charter – externally run schemes with a track record of promoting divisive political concepts including radical gender ideology, ‘decolonisation’ and critical race theory. Even where the goal itself is unobjectionable, such as better collaboration, the criteria require it to be supported by reams of documentation and process. Research England plans to make ‘people, culture and environment’ worth 25 per cent of its assessment criteria for the research it funds – the same as it does real world impact (scientific excellence would also be cut to 50 per cent). In other words, they believe a university’s success at developing the next generation cancer treatments, advancing AI or creating new battery technology should be no more important in determining its funding than its performance on EDI initiatives.⁴²

UKRI announced its initial specifications for the next REF on 15 June, 2023. It introduced several major changes to how it assesses research excellence. One of the most noticeable changes is that the new name for the previous ‘Environment’ criterion has been changed to ‘*People, Culture and Environment*’. As noted by Mansfield, this criterion also has a larger weight of 25 percent, up from 15 percent in 2021. Excellence, in the form of published research, is concomitantly downgraded.

The REF made these changes to widen the meaning of research excellence and ‘ensure that appropriate recognition is given to the people, cultures and environments that underpin a vibrant and sustainable research system.’ The new criterion puts more focus on EDI, with the document stating that ‘it is important that research assessment should support diversity’. This is also shown in a bullet point that mentions that to support EDI, an equality and diversity advisory panel will be kept ‘whose expertise will be further embedded into criteria-setting and assessment processes.’ The REF even suggests that ‘EDI

⁴¹ Gadd, Elizabeth, ‘The battle for people, culture and environment,’ Wonk HE, 7 October, 2025. <https://wonkhe.com/blogs/the-battle-for-people-culture-and-environment/>

⁴² Mansfield, Iain, ‘The Absurdity of Funding ‘Diverse’ Research,’ *Spectator*, 20 January, 2025. <https://www.spectator.co.uk/article/the-absurdity-of-funding-diverse-research/>

data' could be one of the indicators used to measure this criterion.

EDI is set to play a significant role in the exercise due to pressure from activist-oriented academics who self-select into surveys and stakeholder interviews to represent the sector. The REF states that, according to a Future Research Assessment Programme (FRAP) consultation, respondents placed significantly 'more weight on the exercise's impact on research careers and equality, diversity and inclusion than any other aspect of research culture.' The REF also claims that institutions valued 'greater inclusivity' that resulted from REF as 'the majority of those surveyed believe REF 2021 represented moderate or high value for money.'

The provisional equality impact assessment (EIA) that goes with the Future Research Assessment Program (FRAP) emphasises that the 'UK research assessment exercise alone may not give rise to many of the systematic inequalities in the current research ecosystem.' It claims that it is important that 'the future framework supports diversity' instead of 'exacerbating existing inequalities.' The EIA also states that increasing the weight given to the updated criterion will 'ensure that institutions are sufficiently demonstrating equity in their approach to ensuring a submission that is representative of the community, the People, Culture and Environment.' Institutions will be required to explain how 'the outputs submitted are representative of the research and researchers in the disciplinary area within the HEI.' According to the EIA, increasing the weight from 15 percent to 25 percent 'sends a strong message of support for and expectations on HEIs to create, maintain and encourage a positive and inclusive research ecosystem' and is 'likely to have a positive impact on groups with protected characteristics.' They envision universities responding to 'the increased weighting with an equally increased commitment to and investment in EDI.'

FRAP claims that the new weighting is intended 'to shift the focus from the individual to the unit and institutional leadership' to recognize the collaborative nature of research in many fields, such as the health sciences. This said, FRAP states that since funding goes to institutions, not academics, universities should be accountable for how they use the funding to 'produce a stronger university across all dimensions' which includes 'promoting equality and diversity.' FRAP adds that 'diversity matters' and that 'institutions have a moral responsibility' to address 'the past impediment to women and minorities.' None of this is evidenced with rigorous research, but seems instead to be grounded in an unquestioned article of faith.

EDI is not a new factor in funding decisions, yet the UKRI now routinely refers to 'embedding' EDI in everything it does. In a blog post on the UKRI website titled 'Expectations for EDI: - What should we be doing?' UKRI explicitly states that it

wants to 'make it easier to include EDI action within grant proposals and for reviewers to be able to assess this.' In an Annex for a BBSRC (Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council) funding opportunity, EDI is essential as 'partnerships must describe their strategy and actions in a dedicated two-page EDI plan.'

Similarly, the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) funding guide contains a section stating that in its assessment and decision making, it is committed to 'equality, diversity and inclusion' alongside traditional academic values of 'impartiality' and 'transparency.' The Economic and Social Council (ESRC) states in its funding guide that when applicants create an Advisory Group or External Stakeholder Group for their ERSC grant, they are expected to follow best practice, including ensuring that 'when selecting group members, due consideration is given to achieving an appropriate balance in terms of gender and geographical location.' The Medical Research Council (MRC) states that they are 'committed to creating inclusive environments that encourage excellence in research groups through good equalities practice'. Again, class does not appear to fall within the purview of equalities and inclusion.

Another noteworthy point is the increased use of Equality Impact Assessments (EIAs). The UKRI says that they use these 'as a tool to enable us to consider the likely impact of [their] strategies, policies and activity on different groups of people.' As part of an EIA for the 2020/21 Strategic Advisory Network recruitment process, the ERSC says that they 'are keen to increase the number of members with disabilities, from minority ethnic backgrounds, and to ensure diversity of sex, gender identity and sexual orientation among the membership.' A common theme in EIAs is gender identity and pronouns. Staff are advised in some EIAs to add personal pronouns to email signatures where comfortable and to use gender neutral pronouns when preferred pronouns have not been provided. They are advised to monitor their language for bias and avoid using loaded words such as 'Leaders'.

Several individuals on the FRAP International Advisory Group (IAG) appear to be playing an important part in spearheading the new cultural leftism. Dr Chonnetia Jones was a founding partner of the Research on Research Institute (RoRi), whose remit is to make research systems more equitable, diverse and inclusive. Professor Erika Kraemer-Mbula of the IAG edited a publication entitled 'Gender diversity and the transformation of research excellence.' Professor Jane Ohlmeyer, another IAG member, is likewise an outspoken advocate of EDI, with a number of her tweets reflecting strong views on this question. For instance, in a tweet on 9 March 2021 she asked her Trinity College Dublin students to text her directly with any comments on her 'Fairer Trinity: equality, diversity and inclusion' blog and her stated desire to 'actively promote' EDI. True to form, in her role as Chair of the Irish Research Council, Ohlmeyer welcomed the establishment of a gender equality task force for higher education.

Reaction

In the Spring of 2025, a significant number of mainly London and Oxbridge-based academics oriented toward the scientific method, analytic logic, objective truth and excellence raised the alarm over the political hijacking of REF 2029. A letter signed by over 240 faculty, many with leading research profiles, warned that ‘The introduction of a “People, Culture and Environment” (PCE) section, weighted at 25 percent, will weaken the link between research quality and REF performance.’ In addition to the bureaucratic burden of the new requirements, the signatories pointed to the politically-contested nature of the EDI component of PCE: ‘The assessment framework includes a number of criteria whose merit might be legitimately debated such as membership of the Athena Swan scheme and the Race Equality Charter, the creation of safe spaces and the inclusion of EDI activities in the promotion process. This suggests that Research England has pre-judged some approaches as ‘best practice’ when they are in fact contentious.’⁴³

Perhaps in response, the UK Science minister Lord Vallance announced a pause in September 2025 on implementing REF 2029 reforms. He promised further consultation with universities, especially in relation to complaints about increased administrative burden. This is a non-trivial factor given the nearly £500 million spent by the sector on REF 2021, a major commitment of public resources which can only benefit Britain if the discipline it imposes improves research output and communication by a greater amount. In their announcement, four UKRI funding bodies, ‘who jointly own the REF as a UK-wide programme of national research assessment,’ announced that they ‘will use this opportunity to take stock, ensure alignment with government priorities and vision for higher education, and reflect on feedback from the sector. REF will announce any changes to the exercise by December 2025.’⁴⁴ While it is important to consult with academics and universities, it is striking that there was no recognition that the concerns of ordinary taxpayers might conflict with academic priorities for research funding.

The REF has historically maintained a detailed focus on research excellence, with meticulous guidance on how to grade research outputs and aspects of the research environment (such as PhD completions, invited speaker series and research grant funding). In addition to weakening the effectiveness of REF 2029 in rewarding and incentivising excellence in UK research, this politicisation of the research funding process – across both grants and the REF – threatens to undermine the

⁴³ ‘Open letter on Research Excellence Framework (REF) 2029,’ *London Universities Council for Academic Freedom*, 28 April, 2025. <https://lucaf.org/viewdocument.php?id=6>

⁴⁴ ‘Pause to REF 2029 criteria setting and publication of final guidance,’ REF 2029, 4 September, 2025. <https://2029.ref.ac.uk/news/pause-to-ref-2029-criteria-setting-and-publication-of-final-guidance/>

fragile cross-party consensus for funding research that has existed to date in the UK.

A main argument of the EDI forces is that publications, a core component of departments' research rankings, do not measure research significance and reach, and violate EDI because minority groups and women do worse on them. In fact, research shows that metrics capture REF scores quite well, and some countries rely on them entirely.⁴⁵ While textbooks and controversial articles are over-cited and not necessarily a good measure of research excellence, metrics should factor strongly into any assessment regime. Unlike qualitative measures, they are less susceptible to political bias, cronyism and motivated reasoning. They also save considerable funds (approximately £500 million was spent by universities preparing for REF 2021).

Here is a classic equity-efficiency debate in which the cultural socialist side seeks to water down hard metrics of research excellence in favour of more subjective and manipulable cultural socialist considerations. In the words of one EDI proponent: 'Reducing the weight allocated to PCE [People, Culture and Environment aspect of the REF submission] would not only reduce the attention given to promoting positive research cultures, but actually increase the weighting allocated to the element of REF that is most responsible for driving poor research cultures: publications.'⁴⁶ Raw publication rankings, the least worst, and most objective, measure we have of research impact, are viewed as the enemy by EDI proponents within the system.

The goals of promoting economic growth and innovation can be recognised by individuals across the political spectrum. By contrast, the aims of equalizing the distribution of research funds, and of funding work on equality and harm protection over research on social goals such as maximizing economic growth and innovation, are politically contentious. The more that funding is allocated on the basis of the cultural left's priorities rather than those of merit, the greater the likelihood that research will become politically polarising. The net result will be a decline in public trust in UK academic research.

The American Case: A Warning

In the United States, trust in higher education has been declining since 2015. Among Republican voters, confidence in universities dropped from 56 percent in 2015 to 20 percent by 2023-24. The most common complaint from Republican

⁴⁵ Traag, V. A. and L. Waltman (2019). "Systematic analysis of agreement between metrics and peer review in the UK REF." *Palgrave Communications* 5(1). https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-019-0233-x?utm_source=chatgpt.com

⁴⁶ Gadd, Elizabeth, 'The battle for people, culture and environment,' *Wonk HE*, 7 October, 2025. <https://wonkhe.com/blogs/the-battle-for-people-culture-and-environment/>

voters is that faculty are politicizing students. In 2019, nearly 3 in 4 Republicans agreed that American higher education was going in the wrong direction and of these respondents, nearly 80 percent said a reason they felt this was that ‘professors are bringing their political and social views into the classroom.’⁴⁷

Declining trust in higher education set the stage for major policy reform under the newly elected Republican Party in 2025. Early in his second term, Donald Trump issued a series of executive orders and policy shifts targeting Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) programs in federal agencies, contractors, and by extension, higher education institutions. His administration moved to eliminate what it called ‘wasteful’ DEI programs. Universities such as the University of Michigan announced closures of their DEI offices, citing federal directives and the threat of funding cuts. These changes marked a sharp reversal of Obama- and Biden-era support for DEI initiatives.⁴⁸

Federal funding and grants were increasingly tied to compliance with new DEI restrictions. The Department of Justice even issued warnings to universities about certain DEI practices, framing them as potentially unlawful preferences. The rhetoric shifted from DEI as a moral and institutional imperative to DEI as ‘woke ideology’ and reverse discrimination.⁴⁹ In parallel with the DEI rollback, the Trump administration redefined federal research funding priorities and oversight mechanisms. High-profile universities such as Harvard faced threats of losing research grants due to alleged non-compliance with Trump’s anti-DEI agenda. Columbia University reached a settlement to restore federal research funding, agreeing to oversight conditions set by the administration.⁵⁰

The University of Houston reported the termination of 25 federal research awards, with new grant approvals cut by half. These changes reflected shifting federal priorities away from DEI and environmental programs toward defense, domestic energy, and economic competitiveness. More broadly, the administration proposed a new higher education compact in which institutions aligning with its policy objectives would receive preferential treatment. This linked research funding

⁴⁷ Parker, Kim, ‘The Growing Partisan Divide in Views of Higher Education,’ *Pew*, August 19, 2019. <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2019/08/19/the-growing-partisan-divide-in-views-of-higher-education-2/>; Jones, Jeffrey M., ‘U.S. Confidence in Higher Education Now Closely Divided,’ *Gallup*, July 8, 2024. <https://news.gallup.com/poll/646880/confidence-higher-education-closely-divided.aspx>

⁴⁸ Politico, ‘University of Michigan to close DEI office after federal order,’ March 27, 2025. <https://www.politico.com/news/2025/03/27/university-of-michigan-dei-office-00255509>

⁴⁹ ‘Justice Department threatens federal funding over DEI policies,’ *Higher Ed Dive*, April 2025. <https://www.highereddive.com/news/justice-department-threatens-federal-funding-colleges-dei-policies/756510/>; ‘Trump’s DEI crackdown hits U.S. universities,’ *The Guardian*, April 23, 2025. <https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2025/apr/23/trump-education-diversity-hebu>

⁵⁰ ‘Judge rules Trump administration cannot withhold funding from Harvard,’ *Washington Post*, September 3, 2025. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/education/2025/09/03/harvard-trump-administration-lawsuit/>; Thompson, Caroline, ‘Columbia University agrees to pay \$220M in deal with Trump to restore funding,’ *Associated Press*, July 24, 2025. <https://thedailyrecord.com/2025/07/24/columbia-antisemitism-settlement-trump-investigation/>

directly to ideological and administrative compliance.⁵¹

Together, these moves represent a fundamental change in the relationship between the American federal government and universities. Institutions now face increased compliance risks—not only over DEI programming but also in how research aligns with federal priorities. The historical compact between academia and the state, founded on autonomy and the pursuit of knowledge, has shifted toward conditional support based on ideological alignment.⁵²

Conservatives' trust in media has collapsed in the US, Canada and Britain. However, conservative trust in higher education has yet to decline in the UK and Canada as it has in the United States.⁵³ Notwithstanding Britain's apparently delayed trajectory, a survey I conducted of nearly 300 individuals on *Prolific* on 26 October 2025 showed that 41 percent of the 67 respondents who intended to vote Reform in the next election said they mistrusted universities.⁵⁴ This compares to just 13 percent among Tory voters and 7 percent among Labour, Liberal Democrat, Green and regional nationalist voters. Moreover, in October, Nigel Farage appointed James Orr of Cambridge, a longstanding conservative critic of higher education, as his senior adviser.⁵⁵ With Reform leading in the polls and currently on track to form the government, this suggests that major policy reforms to higher education could be in train should a Reform-led government take office in 2029. This must be considered a major risk for higher education that the sector should be trying to address rather than doubling down on the cultural socialist preferences of scholar activists.

Quantitative Trends: Prior Research

To what extent can a culturally leftward shift within Britain's research infrastructure be quantified?

The content of research award abstracts is a good barometer of change since it represents the end product of the research funding enterprise. Abstracts focus on conveying the substantive core of the research, and hence distill the essence of what is valued by researchers and councils. In what follows, we conduct a big data analysis of UKRI awards to track the

⁵¹ Ketterer, Samantha, 'Trump cuts to DEI, green energy among 25 terminated awards at University of Houston,' *Houston Chronicle*, May 14, 2025. <https://www.houstonchronicle.com/news/houston-texas/education/article/university-houston-loses-25-awards-green-energy-20325989.php>; Knott, Katherine, 'Five things to know about Trump's higher ed compact,' *Inside Higher Ed*, October 20, 2025. <https://www.insidehighered.com/news/government/politics-elections/2025/10/20/5-things-know-about-trumps-higher-ed-compact>

⁵² Green, Emma, 'Inside the Trump administration's assault on higher education,' *The New Yorker*, October 13, 2025. <https://www.newyorker.com/magazine/2025/10/20/inside-the-trump-administrations-assault-on-higher-education>

⁵³ Kaufmann, E., 'Political Beliefs of Professors and Public Trust in Higher Education,' *American Political Science Association* meetings, Vancouver, Canada, September 13, 2025.

⁵⁴ Data is referenced in Kaufmann, E., 'Do Britons think Sarah Pochin's comments were racist?,' *Unherd*, 28 October. <https://unherd.com/newsroom/do-britons-think-sarah-pochins-comments-were-racist/>

⁵⁵ Coburn, Poppy, 'Reform's new 'kingmaker': The theologian friend of JD Vance,' *Telegraph*, 19 October. <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/politics/2025/10/19/reform-kingmaker-james-orr-theologian-friend-jd-vance/>

prevalence of politicised concepts.

In the US, work by Rasmussen (2021) finds that, as of 2020, 30 percent of successful National Science Foundation (NSF) grant abstracts mentioned at least one cultural left term, such as ‘equity,’ ‘diversity,’ ‘inclusion,’ ‘gender,’ ‘marginalize,’ ‘underrepresented,’ or ‘disparity’, an increase from 3 percent in 1990.⁵⁶ As Figure 3 shows, the growth in politicised terminology cuts across disciplinary boundaries. While the lines rise over time, there is considerable year-on-year variability in each research council time series.

Figure 3

Source: Rasmussen, Leif, ‘Increasing Politicisation and Homogeneity in Scientific Funding: An Analysis of NSF Grants, 1990-2020,’ *Center for the Study of Partisanship and Ideology (CSPI)*, report no. 4, November 16, 2021.

Canada is closer to the UK in population size and its research funding is organized into three councils, Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (NSERC), Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR) and the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC). Dave Snow of the University of Guelph has discovered a remarkable surge in EDI

⁵⁶ Rasmussen, Leif, ‘Increasing Politicisation and Homogeneity in Scientific Funding: An Analysis of NSF Grants, 1990-2020,’ *Center for the Study of Partisanship and Ideology (CSPI)*, report no. 4, November 16, 2021. <https://www.cspicenter.com/p/increasing-politicization-and-homogeneity-in-scientific-funding-an-analysis-of-nsf-grants-1990-2020>

terminology in Canadian research grants between 1998 and 2021. At SSHRC, where this has been most pronounced, use of the terms transphobia (447 percent increase), Islamophobia (667 per cent), white supremacy (828 per cent) and hate speech (1894 per cent) took off during this period. Figure 4 shows how social justice terms (in aggregate) soared in SSHRC grants between 1998 and 2021.

Figure 4 The prevalence of social justice terms in SSHRC grants.

Source: Snow, D., 'Promoting Excellence or Activism,' p. 34.

Snow further conducted a content analysis of the titles of 2,622 SSHRC grants between 2022 and 2024. In assessing

whether grants were ‘Activist EDI’ in orientation, he used a strict methodology:

I only included projects that clearly adopted language associated with EDI or social justice activism. Examples of such titles include EDI social justice signifiers (such as allyship, intersectional, equity); the use of colonial, decolonial, and settler in a non-neutral way (“Facing Colonial Complicity and Mobilizing Reparations in Canadian Higher Education”); and explicit activism (“Caring for Land, Caring for People: Supporting an Indigenous-led Environmental Stewardship Evaluation Framework”). When there was any ambiguity, only activism in a clear social justice direction (on climate justice, gender identity, and deconstructing society, for example) was coded as “yes.”

Snow discovered that, conservatively, 10-14 percent of awards focused on Activist EDI themes. In some SSHRC grant programmes, SSHRC’s description for applicants and users deployed explicit critical race theory (CRT) language. In these specialised cultural leftist programmes, the share of award abstracts featuring activist EDI content ranged between 42 and 63 percent.⁵⁷

In these cases, radicalism was engineered into the programme design. What follows are phrases from the programme description for the ‘Race, Gender and Diversity Initiative,’ which disbursed 46 grants of up to \$450,000 apiece between 2022 and 2024:

- “Which mechanisms perpetuate White privilege and how can such privilege best be challenged?”
- “What are the current means by which hateful and racist discourses, including by organized hate groups online, are reproduced and gaining momentum in Canada, and how can they best be countered?”
- “How can cisgender and straight masculinity be reinvented for a gender-equitable world?”
- “How has resistance to colonial suppression of nonbinary or matrilineal Indigenous gender systems manifested and persisted, including in oral traditions, and how can it inform action to combat discrimination against transgender, Two-Spirit and non-binary people?”
- “How can we ensure that ableism as well as anti-Black and anti-Indigenous racism in Canada’s health-care system do not lead to coercion and maldistribution of assisted dying?”⁵⁸

⁵⁷ Snow, Dave, ‘Promoting excellence – or activism? Equity, diversity, and inclusion at Canada’s federal granting agencies,’ *Macdonald-Laurier Institute*, February 4, 2025. <https://macdonaldlaurier.ca/promoting-excellence-or-activism-equity-diversity-and-inclusion-at-canadas-federal-granting-agencies/>, p. 42

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 41.

Research Methods

In investigating the UK context, I adopt a related approach to Rasmussen and Snow, using many of the same keywords, in my analysis of the American NSF and Canadian tri-councils' UK equivalent, UKRI. The textual content of grant abstracts and associated metadata were scraped from the UKRI online institutional domain (<https://www.ukri.org/>).

I begin with a similar time period as Rasmussen and Snow's analyses (to 2020), then extend this in a second analysis from 2020 to 2024. I do not analyze other grant elements such as principal investigator names or the institution where the work took place. Tokens were lowercased prior to estimating frequency counts.

Yearly relative frequencies of target unigrams or n-grams in UKRI grants were estimated by dividing the number of occurrences of the target word/n-gram in all grants within a year by the total number of words in all grants in the year. This normalisation of absolute frequency counts controls for variable number of grants in different years, allowing me to compare relative frequencies across time spans irrespective of the total number of grants awarded each year. As may be seen in Figure 5, the number of UKRI grants data available in the 2000–2005 time range is sparse, but the number available expands rapidly in the late 2000s. The total number of grants in my dataset for the 2000–2020 period is 115,480.

Figure 5 Number of UKRI grants per year

In a data analysis of hundreds of thousands of research grants, it is not feasible to manually check the correctness of

frequency counts for all grants. It is conceivable that minor inaccuracies could be present in the analysis due to outlier cases in the underlying HTML or CSS source code in which the textual payload of grants is embedded. This could potentially result in incorrect frequency counts for a small subset of grants. Yet, I am confident that the method overall provides reliable results as illustrated by previous work using similar methodology.⁵⁹ Figure 6 provides an illustrative example of methodological validity: the prevalence in UKRI grants of the revolutionary technique for gene editing, CRISPR, first published in 2013.

Figure 6 Frequency of term CRISPR in UKRI grants

To allow comparison of minimum and maximum frequency usage across terms with different absolute/relative frequencies, we use min-max scaling of frequency counts to normalize the frequency metrics. Min-max scaling rescales the range of relative frequencies to a scale between 0 and 1 (see Equation 1). This approach allows comparison of minimum and maximum frequency usage of the analyzed terms irrespective of their absolute/relative frequency counts.

$$\text{Equation 1} \quad y' = \frac{y - \min(y)}{\max(y) - \min(y)}$$

⁵⁹ Rozado, David, “Prejudice and Victimization Themes in New York Times Discourse: a Chronological Analysis,” *Acad. Quest.*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 89–100, Mar. 2020, doi: <https://www.nas.org/academic-questions/33/1/prejudice-and-victimisation-themes-in-discourse-a-chronological-analysis>; Rozado, “The Prevalence of Prejudice-Denoting Terms in Spanish Newspapers,” MDPI, 2022. <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0760/11/2/33>; D. Rozado, M. Al-Gharbi, and J. Halberstadt, “Prevalence of Prejudice-Denoting Words in News Media Discourse: A Chronological Analysis,” *Soc. Sci. Comput. Rev.*, p. 08944393211031452, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1177/08944393211031452; D. Rozado, “Using Word Embeddings to Analyze how Universities Conceptualize ‘Diversity’ in their Online Institutional Presence,” *Society*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 256–266, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s12115-019-00362-9.

In other words, some terms may appear at many multiples of others (i.e. one term 5 times, another 500 times), but we wish to assess them on the same chart, comparing current to their baseline values. From there, we can also move to aggregate across terms to examine the macro pattern over time.

Results

The average min-max frequencies prevalence in UKRI grants of an aggregated illustrative set of terms encompassing 7 progressive terms is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Min-max scaled frequencies in UKRI grants of individual terms denoting progressive discourse.

Often the frequency of individual terms is too noisy to convey reliable results due to the sparsity of the underlying data and shifts in the popularity of terms, so we provide the aggregate trend in Figure 8. These results echo those of Rasmussen for the NSF and Snow for the Canadian tri-council agencies. That is, they reveal a rise in the frequency of EDI terms in grant abstracts over time. In percentage terms, these keywords appear 2-3 times more often in 2020 than in the mid-2010s and 25-50 times more frequently than in the early 2000s.

Figure 8 Average min-max scale frequencies in UKRI grants of a set of words denoting progressive discourse.

The existing literature suggests that social justice and anti-prejudice terminology greatly increased in academic papers throughout the Anglosphere in the 2010s, though in some cases (racism, sexism, homophobia) high frequency was already present in the 1980s and 90s.⁶⁰ The frequency of an analogous aggregate set of terms denoting prejudice in UKRI grants is provided in Figure 9. By 2020, these terms are 7 times more prevalent than in the mid-2010s and as much as 35 times more prevalent than in the early 2000s. The left's care/harm and equality moral foundations as they concern historically marginalised identity groups have increasingly shaped the UKRI research councils' agenda.

⁶⁰ Rozado, D. (2022). "Themes in Academic Literature: Prejudice and Social Justice." *Academic Questions* 35(2). <https://www.nas.org/academic-questions/35/2/themes-in-academic-literature-prejudice-and-social-justice>

Figure 9 Average min-max scale frequencies in UKRI grants of a set of words denoting prejudice

While there is a notable pattern of growing attention to social justice terminology, there has been some fluctuation for each particular term. The relative frequency in UKRI grants of individual terms denoting social justice discourse is provided in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Relative frequencies in UKRI grants of individual terms denoting social justice discourse.

The time series for individual terms can be noisy due to sample size and the shifting popularity of terms. Aggregating the time series together, however, throws the macro trend into relief, again resembling Rasmussen's results for the NSF in the United States (see Figure 11). In the UK, these terms in 2020 are used at over twice the frequency of 2005-10 and 25 to 50 times the frequency of the early 2000s. The rising focus on issues of concern to the cultural left is a transatlantic

phenomenon, implicating Britain as well as the United States, Canada and other Anglosphere societies.

Figure 11 Average min-max scale frequencies in UKRI grants of a set of words denoting social justice discourse

Trends Since 2020

The previous analysis was linked to the time period used by Rasmussen and Snow. Since 2020, however, EDI terminology has grown dramatically in UK grants, arguably even more so than in previous periods. Extending the analysis to 2024 in Figure 12 shows that mention of the terms ‘equity’, ‘diversity’ or ‘inclusion’ rose fourfold in frequency from the mid-2000s to 2020, then doubled again to 2024. At this point the EDI terms were being deployed at 8 times the rate of the mid-2000s.

Figure 12 Average min-max scale frequencies in UKRI grants of a set of words denoting progressive discourse

The same pattern is evident when we revisit the prejudice term analysis, in Figure 13. The 3-year moving average shows a dramatic rise after 2021. By 2024, the frequency of these terms is above .2 on the scale, twice as high as in 2020.

Figure 13 Average min-max scale frequencies in UKRI grants of a set of words denoting prejudice

The ‘soft’ social justice terms we first visited in Figure 11 (for the period to 2020) follow a similar rising pattern to Figure

13 for the ensuing 4 years. Figure 14 illustrates a continued rising trajectory, reaching a frequency of nearly .40, twice the level of the 2010s.

The explicit EDI focus of REF 2021 and the post-2020 UKRI guidelines on EDI mentioned previously may have encouraged this rise, though it may also have been propelled by the increasingly politicised research agendas of academics. Such individuals may also have self-selected onto appointment panels, helping to shift UKRI priorities in the direction of scholar activism. For example, the AHRC issued a Black Lives Matter statement in 2020, following this up with funding for a scheme to encourage EDI in the Arts and Humanities - with projects worth up to £100,000 apiece. This in addition to a range of other race-related awards and cognate projects such as HateLab.⁶¹

Figure 14 Average min-max scale frequencies in UKRI grants of a set of words denoting social justice discourse

To give a flavour of EDI-focused activist research, journalist Charlotte Gill has catalogued nearly £17 million in UKRI projects pertaining to the Critical Race Theory theme of ‘decolonisation’ and over £4.5 million in radical research at AHRC.⁶² A sample are listed in Table 1. At a time of austerity, when only 1 in 3 British voters can meaningfully be said to support ‘woke’ positions on culture war issues and 3 in 4 say political correctness has gone too far, it is astounding how weakly the signal from voters is penetrating into the insulated world of British research councils.⁶³

⁶¹ ‘Our work on race,’ UKRI, accessed 17 October, 2025. <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/supporting-healthy-research-and-innovation-culture/equality-diversity-and-inclusion/our-work-on-race/>

⁶² See Charlotte Gill Substack, <https://www.charlottegill.co.uk/>

⁶³ Kaufmann, E., ‘The Politics of the Culture Wars in Contemporary Britain,’ *Policy Exchange*, November 19, 2022. <https://policyexchange.org.uk/publication/the-politics-of-the-culture-wars-in-contemporary-britain/>

Table 1. A Selection of Recent Social Justice-Oriented UKRI Projects

Title	Funding
Decolonising Sexual and Gender Based Violence in Higher Education: Interventions in Theory, Policy and Practice	£939,368
Decolonising Peace Education In Africa	£1,997,694
The Heritage and Future of Indigenous Rights within Settler-Colonial Commonwealth Nations in the Environmental Emergency	£1,327,278
The Tipuna Project: Intergenerational Healing, Settler Accountability and Decolonising Participatory Action Research in Aotearoa	£310,724
The Europe that Gay Porn Built, 1945–2000	£841,830
Remediating Stevenson: Decolonising Robert Louis Stevenson’s Pacific Fiction through Graphic Adaptation, Arts Education and Community Engagement	£809,334
Perverse Collections: Building Europe’s Queer and Trans Archives	£136,909
Decolonising the Museum: Digital Repatriation of the Gaidinliu Collection from the UK to India (DiMuse)	£805,769
The Cultural Legacies of the British Empire: Classical Music's Colonial History (1750-1900)	£1,183,769
Trans Performance Now: Glitching Cisgenderism	£185,627
Stolen archives? Re-evaluating the British 'migrated' archives and decolonisation	£201,965
Trans Archiving Network (TAN)	£23,556
Diverse alarums: centering marginalised communities in the contemporary performance of early modern plays	£805,745

Source: Gill, Charlotte, ‘Decolonising Part 1: The UKRI studies costing British taxpayers over £9 million,’ June 24, 2025 ‘Decolonising Part 2: The UKRI studies costing British taxpayers nearly £8 million,’ September 9, 2024; ‘Examples of taxpayer-funded AHRC studies,’ March 26, 2024; *Charlotte Gill Substack* <https://www.charlottegill.co.uk/>.

While this study does not, as Snow’s does, quantify the share of awards that are focused on explicitly cultural socialist EDI themes, the over-time trends in Britain look similar to those in Canada – especially if we extend our purview to 2024.

Applying a conservative estimate of 10 percent of ESRC and AHRC awards (recall the share was more than 10-14 percent for SSHRC grants in Canada for 2022-24) yields a direct annual price tag of £20 million for cultural left activist scholarship.

This is only part of the EDI cost, however. First, many awards contain EDI terminology and diversity considerations, suggesting a cultural socialist frame, even if the research itself is not explicitly activist. Second, there will be a share of Social Justice-themed work in medicine and science, though this will be less than in the social sciences and humanities (Snow and Rasmussen showed lower but still significant levels of EDI terminology among grants funded by medical and STEM councils). To this we must factor in the cost of administering EDI, the time wasted on compliance and dealing with bureaucracy (i.e. satisfying EDI-related requirements in REF 2029), as well as the research output lost through prioritising equity over merit in awarding grant funding. Across the £8.8 billion of annual UKRI funding, this could easily surpass £100 million, but further research is required to quantify the precise amount. A government audit should be undertaken to assess total spend and value for money in this area.

UKRI Institutional Metrics

As with the large-scale keyword analysis of UKRI research projects, it is possible to glean a sense of UKRI's policy direction through a big data analysis of its online documents.

I searched UKRI's web pages, by keyword and date, for the terms 'excellence' and 'equality' to get a sense of where the balance of the organisation's priorities lies and the direction in which it is moving. More pages are available for recent years, which affects the volume of results over time, but the trend is quite stable. Figure 15 reveals that UKRI is more preoccupied with equality than excellence across the years concerned, with a widening gap in favour of equality since 2022. Clearly UKRI feels that values associated with the cultural left are more important than those linked to innovation and the search for truth. This raises serious questions over whether the values of British taxpayers, during a period of growing pressure on public finances, are being reflected in UKRI's £8.8 billion budget.

Figure 15 Keyword frequencies in UKRI web pages, 2020-2025.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

Our examination of the full corpus of UKRI grant abstracts shows a dramatic rise in cultural left terminology since the early 2000s, indicating a growing politicisation of Britain’s £8.8 billion investment in academic research. This emphasis appears strongly in the new REF 2029 guidelines, indicating that universities are being compelled to submit to a growing EDI compliance culture.

This is occurring along two pathways. The first is the culturally leftward shift in academic interests, and the emergence of scholar-activism. This seeks to prioritise politicised research perspectives and subject areas. The second is the institutional and administrative push to mainstream ever more radical EDI approaches in teaching and research, increasingly tracked via measurable goals and timetables.

At a time of scarce resources and rising taxation, the government must take a hard look at how precious funds are being spent. Academic research, whether focused on theory-building or shorter-term imperatives, is important for Britain’s success. All the more reason to ensure that the truth-seeking mission of universities is not diverted toward the political priorities of the identitarian left. This does not mean that research on issues of concern to the cultural left should be completely banned, only that it be assessed against a universally-applicable standard based on rigour and excellence rather than ideology.

The Higher Education (Freedom of Speech) Act 2023 made it clear that the previous government wanted universities to focus on the free exchange of ideas and pursuit of truth, not enforced equal outcomes and emotional safety.⁶⁴ When the country's research funders force applicants to pledge de facto loyalty to these political aims on grant applications or in universities, this violates academic freedom and freedom of conscience, while impairing the search for truth.

Of course it is also true that a nation must make full use of its talent, and remove barriers to entry. If there are policies that can improve access and retention of certain categories of staff, such as women and minorities, this is to be welcomed. However, for this to be the case, two conditions must be met. First, equal representation should be thought of in instrumental terms rather than as an end in itself – as an academic rather than intrinsic goal. After all, if the aim is intrinsic, the money should be diverted immediately to the poorest in society.

While the 'making use of talent' rationale is often cited, systematic evidence that EDI makes a measurable improvement to quantitative metrics of research excellence, or that it advances measures of universities' truth-seeking mission, is lacking. Indeed, there is evidence from citation metrics that EDI tends to reduce research output and impact, undermining excellence.⁶⁵ Second, appropriate safeguards to protect academic freedom and (relatedly) political non-discrimination should be in place. These are currently absent.

Recommendations

As a result of the foregoing, I believe the following changes should be implemented by UKRI:

1. UKRI should rewrite its REF 2029 guidance to eliminate references to EDI as part of the research scoring process and refocus the evaluation criteria for research environment solely on measures of excellence. It should also restore the 60 percent weighting given to submitted outputs that prevailed in REF2021.
2. Government should deduct funding to UKRI by an amount equivalent to its EDI budget (including totals for component councils) until hard metrics of EDI's effectiveness in advancing research excellence are forthcoming.

⁶⁴ <https://bills.parliament.uk/bills/2862>, accessed 11 May, 2023.

⁶⁵ 'Junk Science is being used to Prop up DEI,' *Eric Kaufmann Substack*, October 15, 2024. <https://erickaumann.substack.com/p/junk-science-is-being-used-to-prop>

3. The EDI budget should be removed, though selective small-scale EDI programmes can be piloted using randomised control trials (RCTs). These must result in measurable quantitative improvements in research excellence to be counted as successful.
4. An independent and politically balanced parliamentary commission comprised of non-academics without ties to the sector should investigate whether funding priorities have been skewed too far toward left-wing aims (i.e. equality) rather than conservative goals (cohesion, patriotic attachment, competitiveness) or neutral common aims such as excellence.
5. The government should conduct an audit of UKRI's EDI spend, across all its facets and domains.
6. Universities should cease funding Athena SWAN and reduce funding to Advance HE proportional to the amount it spends on EDI.
7. The overwhelming emphasis on equality and care/harm foundations in research neglects problems related to the moral foundations of group loyalty and the effectiveness of social hierarchies. New funding initiatives should be established for neglected non-leftist priorities such as national attachment and cultural cohesion, national competitiveness, traditional approaches in the arts and humanities, positive sociology, system legitimation and integration, the analysis of left-wing populism and extremism, and the study of virtue and beauty.
8. Any targets or timetables for group representation should be eliminated unless justified by an account of why the funder is falling short of a stipulated 'natural' representation of minority groups (that which would obtain in the absence of discrimination). The natural distribution should be properly justified based on large-N empirical evidence. That is, any targets must be justified by rigorous experimental and multivariate large-N models that show significant evidence of discrimination and which demonstrate that unobtrusive anti-discrimination measures cannot work.
9. Disparities should not be used as evidence of discrimination until experimental or large-N statistical analyses demonstrate this to be true. A broader model of under-representation should be undertaken, using multivariate regression techniques, to identify which characteristics predict grant funding success net of confounding variables, and how large the effect size is. This requires a full-spectrum understanding of inequality that includes class, parental occupation, a wider range of disabilities, intra-racial ethnicity and religion, as well as political views. This model should be used to calibrate any efforts to improve representation.
10. References to systemic or structural discrimination should be removed unless systems/structures can be measured independently of both individual attitudes/discrimination and any outcome measures. Only in this manner can cause and effect relationships be established. For instance, one way of proving systemic discrimination could be to survey academics and uncover that they feel pressure to discriminate against minorities even when they don't wish to.

Another might be that a lopsided gender or ethnic ratio magnifies proven individual-level discrimination. Of course if surveys establish a willingness among individuals to discriminate, this would also provide evidence of the need for anti-discrimination measures.

11. ‘Disparate impact’ alone should not be taken to constitute evidence of structural discrimination. Policies which have disparate impacts on groups should be evaluated to see if such impacts can be limited, but should not be removed if they advance research excellence. Disparate impacts on traditionally advantaged groups such as white Britons and males should also be included in the analysis as the relative position of groups can change. Female underrepresentation in engineering (and any initiatives to improve it) should ideally be mirrored by similar levels of concern over male underrepresentation in education, for instance. Disparate impact should not trump other research aims even as it can remain a secondary consideration.
12. Finally, equity and diversity policies should be required to account for the privileging of certain characteristics (such as race and gender) over others (class, parental occupation, political views) in EDI policy. Unless such a rationale is provided, EDI should be required to pay an equivalent level of attention to as wide as possible an array of group and individual characteristics. That is, there should be ‘equivalent action’ on all major under-represented characteristics equivalent to any action undertaken on race and gender.

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